

Aesthetic Reconstruction of Gingival Black Triangle With Hyaluronic Acid Injection-A Case Report

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Abstract

One of the most common esthetic concerns encountered in clinical practice is the presence of gingival black triangles (GBT), which are triangular-shaped spaces seen between the teeth due to loss or reduction of the interdental papilla. These spaces not only compromise esthetics but also create food lodgment areas, cause phonetic disturbances, and predispose to plaque accumulation, leading to further periodontal problems. Studies have shown that the prevalence of GBT increases with age and is reported to affect up to 38 to 43.7% of adults, with anterior teeth being the most commonly affected.

Keywords

Gingival black triangle; Hyaluronic acid; Interdental papilla; Aesthetic periodontology; Gingival index; Plaque index.

Introduction

Gingival aesthetics play a critical role in the harmony of the smile and overall facial appearance. One of the most common esthetic concerns encountered in clinical practice is the presence of gingival black triangles (GBT), which are triangular-shaped spaces seen between the teeth due to loss or reduction of the interdental papilla. These spaces not only compromise esthetics but also create food lodgment areas, cause phonetic disturbances, and predispose to plaque accumulation, leading to further periodontal problems.¹ Studies have shown that the prevalence of GBT increases with age and is reported to affect up to 38 to 43.7% of adults, with anterior teeth being the most commonly affected.²

The etiology of GBT is multifactorial and includes loss of periodontal attachment, alveolar bone resorption, triangular-shaped crowns, orthodontic tooth movement, and traumatic oral hygiene practices. Tarnow et al. established the importance of the distance between the contact point an alveolar crest in papilla presence; when this

distance exceeds 5 mm, the likelihood of papilla loss increases significantly.³ Considering these factors, management of GBT is a challenging clinical task, requiring both functional and aesthetic rehabilitation.

Objectives

To evaluate the clinical effectiveness of injectable hyaluronic acid in the management of gingival black triangles based upon following objectives such as Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), PPI, GBT both at baseline, 1 & 3-month post intervention.

Materials & Methods

- Gloves
- Mouth mask
- Patient drape
- Betadine
- Mouth mirror
- Vernier calliper
- Ultrasonic scaler
- Injectable Hyaluronic Bellast syringe.

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Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with general good systemic health
- Age range of 18 to 55.
- Patients with (Papillae Presence Index II) and PPI III

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients showing unacceptable oral hygiene.
- Smokers
- Pregnant & Lactating women
- Diastema patients
- Systemically unhealthy
- Patients not ready to give consent.

Clinical Parameter

- Plaque Index (Silness and loe ,1964)
- Gingival Index (Loe and silness,1963)
- Papillae presence index II and III (Cardaropoli et al, 2004)
- Black triangle area. (using Vernier caliper).

Patients presenting with gingival black triangles in the anterior region were selected and received injectable hyaluronic acid. Clinical parameters including Gingival Index, Plaque Index, PPI score and gingival black triangle measurements were recorded at baseline, 1-month, and 3-month follow-up periods. The obtained data were subjected to appropriate statistical analysis utilizing One-way Anova, Bonferroni, Post-Hoc

A : Baseline GBT, B:Measurement of GBT with 15 no. K file, C: Distance of GBT was 1.7mm , D: Infiltration of HA at site, E: GBT at 1 month Follow up, F: GBT at 3 month Follow up

All patients initially underwent Phase I periodontal therapy, which included

1. thorough scaling and root planing using ultrasonic and hand instruments.
2. Oral hygiene instructions were given, and patients were advised to use 0.2% chlorhexidine mouth rinse twice daily for 10 days.
3. Hyaluronic Acid injection (Bellast) is korean – made ,cross linked hyaluronic acid 0.3–0.4 ml of commercially available cross-linked Hyaluronic Acid Bellast) was injected directly into the papillary defect using a micro-syringe under aseptic conditions.
4. Clinical parameters including Gingival Index, Plaque Index, PPI score and gingival black triangle measurements were recorded at baseline, 1-month, and 3-month follow-up periods.

Results

The hyaluronic acid demonstrated statistically consistent and pronounced improvement in PPI values and reduction in gingival black triangle measurements.

Conclusion

HA can be considered a predictable, minimally invasive treatment option for managing gingival black triangles in esthetical demanding areas.

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